

PULSED-GAS DYNAMIC SPRAYING FOR APPLYING COPPER COATINGS ON POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITE TOOLING

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Abstract

A method for producing copper coatings on carbon/epoxy polymer matrix composites (PMCs) is investigated and coated PMCs (CPMCs) are characterised. Characterisation tests include resistance to elevated temperatures and short-beam strength. An integrally heated composite tooling (IHCT) demonstrator is fabricated from CPMCs and is compared with other types of IHCTs.

1 Introduction

Quality and reproducibility of polymer matrix composites (PMCs) are related to the manufacturing process. Traditionally in the aerospace industry, PMCs were manufactured using an autoclave. However, with the advent of larger and more numerous PMCs parts the operational cost is becoming prohibitive which led to the development of out-of-autoclave manufacturing technologies [1].

The National Research Council of Canada – Aerospace Structures and Materials Performance developed an out-of-autoclave process where an integrally heated composite tooling (IHCT) is used for curing PMCs [2]. The IHCT has a PMC structure that provides a lightweight tool and mitigates the mismatch in thermal expansion between the tool and PMC part. Heating is provided by a series of surface heaters. However, placing surface heaters directly on the PMC would result in hot spots due to low PMC thermal conductivity. The solution was to bond a copper sheet on the outer surface of the IHCT for improving heat distribution.

A practical difficulty for manufacturing the IHCT is the forming of the copper sheet. This becomes impractical when the tool features curved shapes and is manufactured in small series. In such cases, applying a thermally conductive metallic coating would be more convenient and would ensure proper thermal contact between the PMC and the copper.

Metallic coatings can be quickly deposited on metals using thermal spray processes. However, using these processes on PMCs may introduce several issues such as poor adhesion, delamination, erosion, melting and thermal degradation [3,4]. That is especially true for epoxy-based PMCs. Nevertheless, Robitaille et al. deposited a zinc coating on carbon fibre/epoxy PMCs using pulsed-gas dynamic spraying (PGDS) [5], a process in which kinetic energy is used for anchoring metallic particles on a substrate by intense plastic deformation. In this case, erosion of the PMC was prevented by co-curing a protective layer on the surface of the PMC, which also enhanced coating adhesion. This co-cured layer featured copper particles embedded in epoxy. The same technique was later used for applying and optimising the density of copper coatings on carbon/epoxy PMCs [6].

Work presented here continued the characterisation of the PGDS coated PMCs (CPMCs) featuring copper coatings. It focuses on the fabrication of the PMC substrates on which coatings are applied, on the CPMCs resistance to elevated temperatures and on their mechanical behaviour. Finally, an IHCT demonstrator was fabricated and the temperature uniformity across its inner surface is compared with that of other types of IHCTs.

2 Experimental

2.1 Substrate

PMC laminates used as substrates for the coatings were made using carbon fibre/epoxy unidirectional prepreg (SE-70, Gurit) with a $[0, 90]_{6S}$ stacking sequence. A layer of pure copper powder (Cu 159-2, Praxair) was manually distributed over the surface of the prepreg stack before cure. The copper powder was produced by gas atomisation and featured

spherical particles ranging from 75 μm to 125 μm in diameter. Prepreg and powder stacks with two different copper loadings, 20g/cm² and 50g/cm², were fabricated. For the higher loading a resin film (SA-70, Gurit) was added on the surface of the prepreg stack to increase the resin content available for infusing through the copper powder bed.

The prepreg and powder stack was vibrated prior to consolidation for improving local distribution of the copper powder. Afterwards, the prepreg and powder were co-cured in an oven using out-of-autoclave vacuum bagging. During cure, excess resin from the prepreg stack seeped through the copper powder, embedding particles on the surface of the laminate and producing the substrate used for coating.

Cross-sections were cut from the substrates for microscopic inspection. Samples were cast in epoxy resin and polished using an automatic polishing machine (Tegrapol-31, Struers). Inspection was then performed using an optical microscope (Olympus XJP-3A), with image analysis (Clemex software) used for measuring the thickness and copper content of the co-cured layer.

2.2 Coating process

Coatings on the substrates were made from two pure copper powders (Fig. 1). The powders were a water atomised powder (Cu 105-3, Praxair) and an electrolytic powder (SST-C5003, Centerline). Particles of Cu 105-3 powder featured an irregular shape with a sub-angular structure and an average diameter of 35 μm . In contrast, particles of SST-C5003 powder featured a grape-like and dendrite structure with a wide array of particle diameter sizes ranging from 5 μm to 45 μm .

The powders were sprayed using a PGDS system (Waverider, Centerline). The process appears in Fig. 2. In this process, a shockwave is used for accelerating a gas in a gun barrel to high velocity. Powder is then injected into the flow and particles are projected towards a substrate. Upon impact with the substrate, the particles undergo significant plastic deformation which enables coating formation from mechanical interlocking. A more thorough explanation of the PGDS process is available in [7].

Coating density can be optimised through several spray parameters including spray gas, gas pressure and gas temperature. Spraying parameters for the

CPMCs used in this study were helium as a propellant gas, at a pressure of 3MPa and temperature of 90°C. These parameters were based on optimisation of copper coatings for carbon/epoxy PMCs presented in a previous study [6].

Cross-sections of the coatings were inspected for porosity through optical microscopy. Inspection followed the same procedure as the one used for the substrate.

2.3 Resistance to elevated temperatures

CPMC samples were subjected to thermal cycling for assessing their resistance to elevated temperatures and thereby addressing one concern regarding their viability in a potential IHCT application. The concern arises from the differences in thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) between the CPMC materials that generate thermal stresses during heating. This potentially leads to damage such as delamination.

Fig. 1. SEM image of copper spray powders, a) Cu 105-3 and b) SST-C5003

Fig. 2. Copper coating a PMC laminate

Two samples were tested for thermal cycling (Fig. 7). The first CPMC sample featured a Cu 105-3 coating that was milled and polished. The sample was 15mm wide, 15mm long and 4.5mm thick. The second CPMC sample featured an as-sprayed SST-C5003 coating. The sample was 25mm wide, 43mm long and 5.5mm thick.

The samples were heated in 4 sequential cycles reaching maximum dwell temperatures of 150°C, 200°C, 250°C and 250°C respectively. A heating cycle consisted in heating a sample in an oven at a rate of 2°C/min up to the specified dwell temperature. The dwell temperature was held for 1 hour. Afterwards, the oven was turned off and the sample was cooled back slowly to room temperature. After each cycle the samples were examined for damage using a stereo-microscope (Ancansco).

2.4 Mechanical behaviour

The short-beam strength test was used for characterising the mechanical behaviour of CPMCs. Testing followed the ASTM D2344 standard [8]. CPMC samples featured milled coating surfaces and were 11.4mm to 12.7mm wide, 30mm to 40mm long and 4.8mm to 5.1mm thick. Thicknesses of the PMC and coatings layers were approximately 2.4mm and 2.2mm respectively. Testing was performed using an Instron 4482 load frame with three-point bending fixtures having 6.3mm radius supports and loading nose, and a span of 25.5mm. Loading was applied at a rate of 1mm/min.

The change in mechanical behaviour due to increasing temperatures was assessed using an environmental chamber (Instron 3111) installed on the load frame. Samples were tested at 25°C, 70°C and 120°C. These temperatures were selected based on the 99°C glass transition temperature T_g of the PMC used in this study. This T_g was measured from the differential scanning calorimeter (Q1000, TA Instruments) results obtained by Hugo Laurin at National Research Council of Canada – Aerospace Manufacturing Technology Center.

In addition to the short-beam strength values, classical bending theory was used in developing bending and shear stresses equations for CPMCs. Equations are based on uniform width multilayered composite beams [9]. For n number of layers, the axial bending stress σ_x in a specific layer i is given by:

$$\sigma_{x,i} = -\frac{M}{\sum_{j=1}^n E_j I_j} y_n - y E_i \quad (1)$$

where M is the bending moment, y_n is the location of the neutral axis, y is the distance from the bottom surface of the beam, E is the flexural modulus of elasticity, I is the second moment of area, and subscripts i and j represent material layers.

Similarly, the shear stress τ_{xy} in a layer i is given by:

$$\tau_{xy,i} = -V \frac{\sum_{k=1}^i \left[\int E y dy \right]_k}{\sum_{j=1}^n E_j I_j} \quad (2)$$

where V is the shear force and subscript k represents a material layer. The moduli in equations (1) and (2) are taken as 100GPa for the copper coating based on literature [10] and 7GPa for the co-cured layer based on the Mori-Tanaka model [11]. The flexural moduli of the PMC layer were experimentally measured at 70GPa, 60GPa and 15GPa at temperatures of 25°C, 70°C and 120°C.

It is important to note that stress values calculated from equations (1) and (2) only provide rough estimates for comparing the samples in this current study. This is because the equations assume a completely elastic behaviour without any slippage

between layers and mostly because they do not account for the complex stress field caused by the combined bending, shear and compression.

2.5 Tooling demonstrator

A flat heated plate demonstrator (Fig. 3.a) was fabricated for investigating the use of CPMCs as a potential IHCT material. The demonstrator measured 150mm by 150mm and featured a 4mm thick cross-ply PMC layer, a 0.35mm co-cured layer and a 2mm thick SST-C5003 copper coating. The coating was sprayed using the same parameters as for the samples used for thermomechanical characterisation. The coating was polished and machined locally for providing a smoother contact surface with the heater. Heating was provided by a 75cm² surface heater (MINCO) bonded onto the copper coating surface of the demonstrator. The top and bottom surfaces of the demonstrator were insulated using a 140mm thick insulation blanket (R24, Roxul) for minimising heat losses.

The demonstrator was heated for 800s by supplying 15W to the heater. An infrared camera (i7, FLIR) was used for characterising the surface temperature distribution across the demonstrator inner PMC surface after heating.

The surface temperature distribution of the demonstrator (plate #1) was compared to the ones of two other heated plate demonstrators. These plates

measured 150mm by 150mm and featured a 4mm thick PMC layer. Plate #2 only consisted in a bare PMC with a bonded heater (Fig. 3.b) while plate #3 additionally featured a 1.6mm thick bonded copper sheet (Fig. 3.c). It should be noted that design of plate #3 was based on the IHCT presented by in [2].

3 Results

3.1 Substrates

The coating substrates produced were smooth on the PMC side and rough on the co-cured copper layer side despite the use of a caul plate. Large amounts of powder were not wetted by the resin which resulted in exposed copper particles that caused some of the observed roughness. The non-uniform resin flow inside the copper powder bed also prevented the embedding of a constant copper thickness, which caused elongated depressions oriented in the fibre direction.

Measurements through image analysis of the substrate (Fig. 4) revealed that the thickness of the co-cured copper layers were $350\mu\text{m} \pm 120\mu\text{m}$ and $700\mu\text{m} \pm 135\mu\text{m}$ for laminates having copper loadings of 20g/cm² and 50g/cm², respectively. The copper content was measured at around 57% and was unaffected by the initial copper or resin contents.

Fig. 3. Integrally heated tooling demonstrators featuring: a) a coated PMC (plate #1), b) a bare PMC (plate #2) and c) a PMC with a bonded copper sheet (plate #3)

Fig. 4. Cross-sectional image of copper particles co-cured on a PMC laminate

3.2 Copper coatings

Coating porosity was measured by cross-sectional image analysis of CPMC samples. Coatings produced using powder Cu 105-3 saw limited deformation of spray particles. This is suggested by the numerous voids present between particles (Fig. 5). Coatings produced using similar parameters as the ones presented in this study had a porosity that was previously reported at around 3-4% [6].

In contrast, coatings made using powder SST-C5003 saw significant deformation of the sprayed particles as noted by the absence of any notable voids (Fig. 6.a). However, the dendritic structure of SST-C5003 makes the particles prone to breakage.

Broken particles form a fine dust that scatters across the substrate and it is often trapped into surface depressions (Fig. 6.b). This prevents

adequate contact and bonding between the coating and the co-cured copper particles of the substrate.

3.3 Resistance to elevated temperatures

The Cu 105-3 and a SST-C5003 CPMC samples that were thermally cycled appear in Fig. 7. During testing, both samples showed an identical behaviour towards elevated temperatures cycling.

After the first one hour cycle at 150°C, the copper surface started oxidising. No visual signs of coating spallation were observed and microscopic observations did not reveal any delamination or damage. The following cycle at 200°C further oxidised the copper coating of the samples. The coatings tarnished to a dull bronze colour but no samples showed signs of damage. Microscopic investigation of the following cycle at 250°C revealed that around the edges of the samples some copper particles of the co-cured layer were forced out of the CPMC. Their number increased after the second cycle at 250°C. However, coating spallation was not observed.

3.4 Mechanical behaviour

Two loading scenarios were used for the short-beam strength test. The first scenario had the loading nose of the three-point bending fixture pressing against the coating side of the samples, subjecting the coatings to axial compressive stresses. The second scenario had the loading nose pressing against the PMC side, subjecting the coatings to axial tensile stresses.

Fig. 5. Cross-sections at magnifications 100X (left) and 400X (right) of Cu 105-3 coatings on the co-cured copper layer

Fig. 6. Cross-sections at magnifications 100X (left) and 400X (right) of SST-C5003 coatings on the co-cured copper layer a) without spray particle breakage and b) with spray particle breakage

Fig. 7. CPMC samples used for resistance to elevated temperatures testing, before and after thermal cycling

The numbers of samples tested for each loading scenario appear in Tab. 1. Shortage of spray powder Cu 105-3 limited the number of samples and prevented any testing at elevated temperatures.

Short-beam strength testing revealed that both Cu 105-3 and SST-C5003 CPMC samples exhibited identical fracture behaviour.

Loading on the coating side always resulted in failure through coating delamination. At failure, a crack appeared at the sample edges and it instantaneously propagated up to the sample centre along the substrate-to-coating interface. The crack then deviated to shear the coating through its thickness (Fig. 8). The weakest area was the co-cured layer-to-coating interface, as some coating and spherical co-cured layer particles were observed on both fracture surfaces.

Average short-beam strengths for this loading case appear in Fig. 9, where error bars represent the maximum and minimum values measured. At room temperature, the 1450N force at failure of the Cu 105-3 samples was higher than the 940N of the SST-C5003 samples. The prior also showed much lower variability.

At elevated temperatures, no trend could be identified for the SST-C5003 samples due to the limited number of samples tested and to the high variability observed at room temperature.

For the second loading case, failure occurred at a lower force than in the first loading case. Loading on the PMC side always resulted in a brittle coating fracture in tension. At failure, a crack initiated on the outer coating surface at mid-span and propagated instantaneously in the thickness of the CMPC until stopped by the tougher co-cured layer. At that point, the coating remained attached to the CMPC. As seen in Fig. 10, upon applying a considerably greater amount of force, delamination of the coating occurred.

Tab. 1. Numbers of samples tested for short-beam strength

CPMC coating	Testing temperature	Number of samples	
		Loaded on coating	Loaded on PMC
Cu 105-3	25°C	3	3
	25°C	3	3
SST-C5003	70°C	1	3
	120°C	1	3

Average short-beam strengths for this loading case appear in Fig. 11, where error bars represent the maximum and minimum values measured. At room temperature, in contrast to the previous loading case, the 420N force at failure of the Cu 105-3 samples was much lower than the 760N of the SST-C5003 samples. Results also showed much lower variability for both types of coatings compared to the first loading case.

At elevated temperatures, the force at failure of SST-C5003 samples decreased non-linearly with temperature. Below T_g of the PMC, the forces at failure were similar whereas above T_g the force at failure fell to 440N.

Fig. 8. CPMC failure due to coating delamination

Fig. 9. CPMC short-beam strengths with coating subjected to axial compression

Fig. 10. CPMC brittle coating fracture

Fig. 11. CPMC short-beam strengths with coating subjected to axial tension

3.5 Tooling demonstrator

Infrared images of the three heated plate demonstrators after heating appear in Fig. 12. Plate #2 with its lack of thermally conductive layer showed great surface temperature difference of 73°C between the maximum and minimum values recorded.

Plate #3 with its bonded copper sheet achieved a major improvement in temperature uniformity. The difference in surface temperatures lowered to 6°C.

Results for plate #1 showed that despite the coating being slightly thicker than the copper sheet of plate #3, hot spots were still observed beneath the heater. However, compared to plate #2, the copper coating enabled significant improvement of the in-plane thermal conductivity which lowered the temperature difference across its inner surface to 9°C.

Thermal uniformity of the heated plate demonstrators was characterised by the standard deviation of the inner PMC surface temperatures. Plate #2 showed the worst uniformity with a standard deviation of 20°C. Plate #1 with its sprayed coating offered the second best uniformity with a standard deviation of 1.6°C which was not too far from the 0.9°C of plate #3.

Fig. 12. Infrared thermal images after 800s of heating at 15W for a) plate #1, b) plate #2 and c) plate #3

4 Discussion

4.1 Substrates

All substrates were cured with excess copper powder which resulted in rough substrate surfaces. Additionally, it was shown that greater resin content in the prepreg stack could be used for embedding a thicker co-cured copper layer in the substrate. However, this method of using excess powder provides no accurate control over the thickness or distribution of the copper particles in the co-cured layer, meaning that the initial thickness homogeneity provided by vibrations was lost. Better thickness control can potentially be achieved with a resin rich content which would enable complete infusion of the copper powder bed. However, this would leave a resin rich surface which adversely affects deposition of a copper coating as reported in [12]. Hence, despite its lack of control over the co-cured layer the method of using an excess amount of copper powder currently remains the best option for fabricating substrates.

4.2 Resistance to elevated temperatures

The lower short-beam strength of SST-C5003 samples observed when the coating is subjected to axial compressive stresses suggests that these samples would be more prone to thermal delamination than Cu 105-3 samples. However, both Cu 105-3 and SST-5003 samples resisted delamination up to at least 250°C, which more than meets the requirements for an IHCT application. It is conjectured that this outcome was facilitated by the presence of the co-cured layer with its embedded copper particles that helped bridge the difference in CTE between the layers, reducing the risk of delamination.

4.3 Mechanical behaviour

Short-span strength results showed two main failure modes of CPMCs depending on the loading case: delamination and coating fracture.

Cu 105-3 samples were on average more resistant to delamination and their force at failure was much more consistent than SST-C5003 samples. This behaviour can be linked to the quality of the co-cured layer-to-coating interface. Microscopic inspections performed (Fig. 6) revealed that in some

cases SST-C5003 particles underwent breakage which left dust particles at this interface. The presence of dust prevented adhesion between the coating and the substrate. Depending on the surface coverage of the dust, coating adhesion will vary significantly. Hence, PGDS coatings on PMCs should favour spray powders with minimal particle breakage for improved delamination resistance.

Conversely, SST-C5003 coatings featured much higher resistance to tensile loads than Cu 105-3 coatings. This implies that the prior has higher coating cohesion strength, which for PGDS coatings is related to better interlocking of the sprayed particles. Optical microscopy (Fig. 6) revealed that coating porosity was much lower and sprayed particles were more deformed in the case of SST-C5003 coatings compared to Cu 105-3 coatings. This increased the contact area between particles and promoted cohesion in the coating. Hence, coating porosity of CPMCs should be minimised to maximise mechanical properties.

Based on the failure mode obtained through the short-beam strength tests, stresses at failure can be calculated from Eq. (1-2) for axial and shear stresses.

For the scenario in which the load was applied on the coating, delamination occurred due to shear stresses. The maximum shear stress at the co-cured layer-to-coating interface was calculated using in-plane stress transformation, and results appear in Fig. 13. An average shear strength of 19MPa was calculated for Cu 105-3 samples. In contrast, a wide range of shear strengths, 7MPa to 17MPa, was calculated for SST-C5003 samples due to the imperfections at the coating interface as noted above.

For the scenario in which the load was applied on the PMC, coating fracture was caused by the tensile stresses at the surface of the coating. The maximum axial stresses are presented in Fig. 14. An average tensile strength of 59MPa was calculated for Cu 105-3 samples whereas an average tensile stress of 96MPa was calculated for SST-C5003 samples. For the latter, results show that the coating stress at failure is not affected by temperatures, in the range tested. Hence, the reduction of short-span strength with increasing temperature reported earlier was caused by the reduction in rigidity of the PMC due to temperatures greater than T_g .

Fig. 13. Shear strength of the co-cured layer-to-coating interface

Fig. 14. Tensile strength of the coatings

Moreover, tensile values for both types of coatings were lower than for annealed copper at room temperature (209MPa [13]). This difference is explained by the nature of PGDS coatings, where most of the cohesion originates from spray particle-to-particle mechanical interlocking which is weaker than metallic bonding. It is nonetheless observed that increasing coating density provides strength closer to bulk values.

4.4 Tooling demonstrator

Results of the temperature uniformity across the inner surface of tooling demonstrators showed the importance of a conductive layer on PMCs for

improving their in-plane thermal conductivity and minimising hot spots.

Results also showed that for a similarly thick layer, a bulk sheet of copper provides superior thermal conductivity than a copper coating. The lower performance of the copper coating is explained by interfacial defects between the sprayed particles of the coating. This lack of complete metallic bonding reduces conductivity. Nonetheless, copper coatings made with PGDS can still significantly improve thermal conductivity of PMCs.

The lower conductivity of the sprayed coatings is compensated by certain advantages that they provide over formed copper sheets. They include the potential for being easily applied onto curved surfaces and for the ability of changing the thickness of the conductive layer locally. Hence, some performance is traded for simpler manufacturing.

5 Conclusion

This work showed a method for producing copper coatings on PMCs successfully. The method relied on using the PGDS spraying process coupled with co-curing a layer of embedded copper particles on the surface of PMCs for enabling sprayed coatings. This co-cured layer and coated PMCs (CPMCs) were characterised. Characterisation of the co-cured layer provided some insight towards the fabrication of substrates used for coating. Characterisation of the CPMCs showed that they can resist delamination from thermal stresses when heated up to 250°C. CPMC mechanical behaviour was characterised through the short-span strength test which revealed their two main modes of failure, which are delamination at the co-cured layer-to-coating interface and tensile fracture of the coating. Finally, a heated plate demonstrator made with CPMC was compared with other types of demonstrators. Results showed the viability of CPMC for a future integrally heated composite tooling application.

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References

- [1] Walczyk D., and Koppers J., 2012, "Thermal press curing of advanced thermoset composite laminate parts," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **43**(4), pp. 635–646.
- [2] Raizenne D., Hind S., and Poupore J., 2006, "Integral heating for composite tooling," *Proceedings of the 6th Canada-Japan workshop on composites*, Canadian Association for Composite Structures and Materials.
- [3] Liu A., Guo M., Gao J., and Zhao M., 2006, "Influence of bond coat on shear adhesion strength of erosion and thermal resistant coating for carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting polyimide," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **201**(6), pp. 2696–2700.
- [4] Lupoi R., and O'Neill W., 2010, "Deposition of metallic coatings on polymer surfaces using cold spray," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **205**(7), pp. 2167–2173.
- [5] Robitaille F., Yandouzi M., Hind S., and Jodoin B., 2009, "Metallic coating of aerospace carbon/epoxy composites by the pulsed gas dynamic spraying process," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **203**(19), pp. 2954–2960.
- [6] Gosselin S. B., Yandouzi M., Jodoin B., and Robitaille F., 2011, "Characterization of cold sprayed copper coatings for carbon fibre/epoxy composite moulds," *Proceedings of the 26th ASC Technical Conference*, Sept. 26-28, Montreal, Canada, pp. 1–16.
- [7] Jodoin B., Richer P., Bérubé G., Ajdelsztajn L., Erdi-Betchi A., and Yandouzi M., 2007, "Pulsed-gas dynamic spraying: process analysis, development and selected coating examples," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, **201**(16-17), pp. 7544–7551.
- [8] D2344/D2344M - 00 A. S., 2006, *Standard test method for short-beam strength of polymer matrix composite materials*, ASTM International, Barr Harbour, PA, USA.
- [9] Popov P. E., 1998, *Engineering mechanics of solids*, Prentice Hall Inc., Upper Saddle River, New Jersey USA.
- [10] Luzin V., Spencer K., and Zhang M.-X., 2011, "Residual stress and thermo-mechanical properties of cold spray metal coatings," *Acta Materialia*, **59**(3), pp. 1259–1270.
- [11] Dai L. H., Huang P., and Wang R., 1998, "A generalized self-consistent Mori-Tanaka scheme for prediction of the effective elastic moduli of hybrid multiphase particulate composites," *Polymer Composites*, **19**(5), pp. 506–513.
- [12] Gosselin S. B., Yandouzi M., Jodoin B., and Robitaille F., 2011, "Thermally conductive coatings for polymer-matrix composites using cold spray," *Proceedings of the 58th CASI Aeronautics Conference*, Apr. 26-28, Montreal, Canada, pp. 1–10.
- [13] Davis J. R., 2001, "Properties of pure copper," *ASM Specialty Handbook: Copper and Copper Alloys*, ASM International, Materials Park, OH, USA, pp. 446–452.